

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dattani's Women's Take on the New Woman: A Comparison with Ibsen's Nora

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Accepted version published on 1st November 2025

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17504738>

ABSTRACT

This research paper aims to compare Mahesh Dattani's female characters to Nora, the brave and revolutionary female character in Henrik Ibsen's *A Doll's House*. The researcher examines how Dattani's female characters respond to the concept of the "New Woman" and how their growing consciousness empowers them to resist the strict norms of patriarchal society. With their resistance, struggle, and assertion of personal identity, these women challenge established boundaries and the standards imposed by the phallogocentric society. On the other hand, Ibsen's problem play demonstrates how an apparently modest housewife, like Nora, develops into a strong symbol of autonomy and self-realisation. Both writers highlight the limits put on women in a phallogocentric culture and call for reform. The so-called "Second Sex" eventually learns to break free from epistemic violence, recover autonomy, and find the strength to struggle for dignity, equality, and identity. This comparative research highlights the growth of female agency in modern play.

Keywords: new woman; patriarchal society; problem play; phallogocentric

FULL RESEARCH PAPER

Introduction

The concept of a 'problem play' in literature emerged in the 19th century, a genre that dealt with showcasing social issues prevalent in society realistically. One of the famous writers who followed this style was Henrik Ibsen, who contributed notable works like *A Doll's House* (1879) and *Ghosts* (1882). Problem plays mainly focus on presenting social issues rather than offering solutions to them. With this, writers began to take up this genre for their writing. Among the admirers of Henrik Ibsen, a famous contemporary writer, is Mahesh Dattani. Dattani can be found among those writers who write for classes of society that have never been considered important, or rather are treated as marginalised. Such sections are mainly transgender individuals, homosexuals, and women. It is observed that society views male and female as the only natural sexes. However, in reality, the mainstream culture is phallogocentric. One of his famous plays, "*Bravely Fought the Queen*," can be considered a perfect problem play, which is examined in this paper in relation to the New Woman.

To question this phallogocentric society and to get away from the patriarchal notions of it, the concept of the New Woman emerged at the end of the 19th century. This term was used to describe a woman who pushes herself beyond the limits imposed by society and tries to establish her own space by being representative. While discussing Ibsen and Dattani, one can observe that both writers have adopted this concept. Therefore, I argue that the patriarchal society pushes women by abusing them physically, emotionally, and socially, to consciously step into the shoes of the New Woman, questioning the socially constructed gender roles.

Physical Violence as a Catalyst for a New Woman

Women have always been objectified in a patriarchal society. They are treated as marginalised, who are not allowed to raise their voice against the abuse done to them. Moreover, if spoken, they are unheard. As Simone de Beauvoir puts it, they are the second sex of the male-dominant society. Dattani's play *Bravely Fought the Queen* takes its title from a famous Hindi poem about the Rani of Jhansi, 'Khub ladi mardani wo to Jhansi wali Rani thi.' This shows that if a woman fights bravely, she is then called a 'manly queen.' In our society, women are "expected" to be fragile. Moreover, if she fights, she is considered a man. The title of the play itself reveals the generalised behaviour of society. In this play, Jiten and Nitin Trivedi are brothers who are working on an advertisement for ladies' nightwear. For that, they decided to get some

feedback from the customers. Women customers rejected the idea of buying such attractive nightwear and opposed their views. The point comes when Jiten says that there is no point in asking women about such things. However, women were the only consumers. He believed that man should be asked about this idea because in the end, a woman wears just to attract a man physically.

Jiten is shown as an embodiment of the patriarchal society. For him, women are just sex objects and can be treated as society wants. Women get conditioned to physical abuse to a great extent that they start feeling that to control a woman, a man should beat his wife. Baa, mother of Jiten and Nitin, deliberately orders her son to beat his pregnant wife. Her husband treated her badly when she was young. He used to beat her hard that she would request him not to beat her face. She got so conditioned to it that she didn't want society to know about her husband beating her. However, when it came to her pregnant daughter-in-law, Dolly, she wanted her son to beat her on the face and not on the stomach just to save the life of her grandchild.

BAA. No! Jitu, hit her on the face but not on the ... stop it, Jitu! On the face, only on the face! Enough! Stop! (Dattani 311)

In Ibsen's *A Doll's House*, Nora has been treated so badly by her husband without knowing the reality. She felt humiliated, and thinks that she has always been treated as a 'doll' by her husband. Moreover, thus, despite such a strong relationship, her husband never thought before humiliating her. With such treatment, women began to adopt the concept of the New Woman, where they decided to raise their voices against such abuses. Dattani's play *Seven Steps Around the Fire* portrays the character of Uma, who, despite society's dominant views, chooses to fight for the rights of a *hijra*. This shows how women step into the shoes of becoming New Women. She dared to raise a voice against the physical exploitation that was also towards a *hijra*.

Emotional Trauma and the Rise of the New Woman

Women are considered emotionally weak in society. The society is phallogocentric, which works considering males as the only dominant sex of the society. When a woman decides to become independent, society often considers her decision a response to men, seeking to showcase her talents. However, then the question arises as to why a woman should show off? Can't she work just for her personal satisfaction and liking? Society has associated certain gender roles with it. These are socially constructed. Judith Butler, in her work *Gender Trouble*, talks about such gender roles. She says that in a general sense, sex is biologically constructed, and

Gender is socially constructed. However, by giving the relevance to the discursive and prediscursive idea of Foucault, she believes that sex has also become socially constructed, where certain sex roles are assigned to males and females. Under that, if a woman tries to work, she is made to realise that women don't work.

In Dattani's play *Bravely Fought the Queen*, Lalitha grows bonsai professionally just because she likes it. Moreover, when she and her husband won the prize of either accepting cash or tickets to Goa, Lalitha wanted money, and Shridhar wanted to visit Goa. Lalitha worried about her plants and decided not to go. To this, Shridhar believed that she refused to go just because she wanted to show that she was independent. On the other hand, Nora worked secretly so that she could earn money and could bear the cost of going to Italy. However, here, Nora had to keep this secret from her husband. All these factors emotionally affect the woman, causing her to question her identity within society. With this, a woman chooses to make herself representable in society.

Social Stigma and the Fight for Identity

In a patriarchal society, man is considered to be the dominant gender and are the only representable gender in society. Based on a man, a woman is given her identity. Society plays a major role in abusing women and leading them on the path of accepting the idea of the New Woman. According to society, Dolly is a typical daughter-in-law who takes care of her mother-in-law. Jiten and Nitin expect the same thing from her, i.e., not to leave the house and take complete care of Baa. Society has always played a major role in marginalising women. They are considered subaltern. Now, when we speak of giving voice to the subaltern, one thinks of Spivak's work, "Can the Subaltern Speak?" This work doesn't question whether women can speak, but rather whether they are allowed to speak. Society has always been controlling women, especially this society, which is already phallogocentric. Even if women try to come out of the margins, they are not allowed to raise their voice. However, the centre speaks for them. They have become the object of the Subject (with capital S), which is present at the centre.

Dattani's Alka (wife of Nitin) is shown in this play as a woman who is highly involved in drinking. With this, she tries to purge her emotions, her sufferings, etc Baa keeps Nitin away from her so that they cannot have a child. Dattani, with his play *Seven Steps Around the Fire*, shows how hijras are not considered as the natural sex of society, and heteronormativity is deemed to be the only accepted sexual orientation in society. However, in this play, when it comes to marginalising women, homosexuality is

completely ignored. For dominant Nitin, his homosexual relationship with Praful (his wife's brother) is not a big deal for him or for society. Here, we can see that for two men to have a relationship, one gets his sister married to the other. Alka got nothing but just the name of her husband. She is used as a thing of exchange so that men can fulfil their desires. Whereas, in Ibsen's *A Doll's House*, Nora is also used as a commodity not only by her husband but also by Krogstad, who uses her and her secret to regain his job, which Nora's husband rejected. With such treatment of women, they deliberately choose to come out of the margins and raise their voice, as seen when Nora shuts the door, and that sound marks the step taken by Nora to wear the shoes of the New Woman. Dolly, at the end, speaks her heart out, which makes Jiten understand his mistake and the fault behind his daughter's disability. She, in the end, is found to raise her voice for her sister, Alka, and to speak out against her mother-in-law's behaviour.

Conclusion:

The paper showcases Dattani's female characters, who discover their strength and move towards embracing the identity of the New Woman. His plays focus on how patriarchy has always been objectifying women, presenting males as the only subjects of society. Dattani has consistently drawn inspiration from Henrik Ibsen's plays, as evident in his works. Women are pushing themselves out of the patriarchal boundaries and freeing themselves from the suffocating dominance of society. As literature is a 'mirror of society,' this study tries to focus on how the necessity of understanding the drawbacks of patriarchy, which is promoted both by men and women, affects both the sufferers and perpetrators of it. Voices of women are clearly heard from the stage in a way that will keep on echoing till eternity. The paper opens up the space for further research on problem plays, allowing for comparisons between different problem plays.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The data sharing policy does not apply to this article.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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